

MAKING INCLUSIVE EDUCATION A REALITY: THE ROLE OF TEACHERS, PARENTS AND ADMINISTRATORS

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Abstract:

The study used basically a survey design which employed the quantitative approach to investigate how children with special learning needs (SENs) are supported to learn together in the inclusive classroom with the focus on finding the level of support for children in five (5) inclusive schools in the Cape Coast Metropolis, Ghana. The sample size involved 86 teachers, 6 administrators (Head teachers) and 40 parents. In all, a total of 132 participants were involved in the study. Questionnaire was designed in close-ended format for the teachers, administrators and parents. The basic structure of the instrument was based on four Point Likert-type scales. The Likert-scale items questionnaire was analysed using frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviation. A tally sheet was used to generate frequency counts out of which percentages were calculated based on the scores assigned to each rating. These data were then analysed using the SPSS computer system. It was found from the study that, there are low levels of material or human support for pupils with special educational needs in inclusive classrooms. On material support, the parents indicated that their children do not receive any material support from Ghana Education Service to support their children and they do not get any financial support from Non-Governmental Organizations (NGO's). It is recommended that teachers, parents and administrators should come together to provide the needed support for pupils with special education needs to ensure the success of the inclusive agenda.

Keywords: inclusive classroom, special learning needs, inclusive education

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1. Introduction

The recent drive for enrolment of children into regular schools has made classrooms to be over crowded with both children with special needs and those without. This has compounded the already existing problem in the regular education classroom where individual attention was rarely provided. A visit to some schools by the researcher revealed an overcrowded classroom with pupils with varied learning needs. A personal conversation with a class teacher revealed that, quite a number of pupils in the classroom has various learning difficulties and disabilities that require extra attention, but no support has been provided by the Ghana Education Service. The resource teachers who give assistance to teachers on how to cater for the differential needs of learners are very few. The teachers in the schools are confronted with a lot of problems, the worst being over crowded classroom, which affect their class management and teaching strategies. The nature of children's composition in the basic education classroom requires appropriate support from teachers, administrators, and parents in order to meet the differential learning needs of SEN children in inclusive classroom. However, an observation and interaction with some teachers in one of the targeted schools revealed that pupils' enrolment has increased yet it appears the needed support services they require to meet children's learning needs are not provided. These observations appear to be consistent with Bryans's (1997) assertion that pupils without disabilities as well as teachers in the general education classroom usually do not accept pupils with special needs in schools. More so, the large pupil-teacher ratio in the schools appears to be one major factor for teachers not meeting the differential learning needs of children especially those children with special learning needs. It also appears that even though, the schools have high enrolment, and special education resource teachers do not visit these schools regularly. Many studies have been conducted on the evaluation of inclusive education in some parts of Ghana but on support for children with SEN in the inclusive education, there is still more studies to be done.

2. The Purpose of the Study

The study examined the teacher, administrative and parental support for pupils with special educational in inclusive classrooms in the Cape Coast Metropolis.

2.1 Objectives of the Study

- 1) To determine the levels of support needed in the inclusive schools for teaching different categories of children.
- 2) To investigate what special supports exist in the school.

2.2 Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- 1) What levels of support is required for meeting the differential learning needs of pupils with special educational needs in inclusive classroom?
- 2) What special educational support exists in inclusive classrooms for pupils with special educational needs?

3. Literature Review

3.1 Level of Support Required for Meeting the Differential Learning Needs of Children with SEN in Inclusive Schools

The following resources have been identified by literatures as supports that teachers can provide to pupils with special educational needs in their school. The resources have been put into two levels namely; human resource and material resource. Human resource consists of personnel in the area of special education who provides services for children with special educational needs. In the context of this study, the following human resource supports are considered:

3.2 Resource Teachers' Services

For general education teachers to be effective and efficient in providing support for pupils with special educational needs in inclusive classrooms, they rely on the services of resource teachers. This service aims at placing and supporting SEN students in inclusive classrooms to enable them to achieve the best in learning. Resource teachers are specialists who are trained and attached to the district education offices and they go from school to school to identify, assess children and plan management programmes for regular teachers to enable them support students with SEN in their teaching and learning (Special Education Department, 2007).

Baine (2001) pointed out that these specialists are consultants who travel from school to school to assist teachers in methods of assessment, instructions, materials preparation and equipment building. Okyere and Adams (2003) opined that in most of the mainstream schools in Ghana, specialist teachers of students with SEN provide resource room support. The bulk of the teachings are done by the regular classroom teachers while the exercises of the visually impaired are transcribed by the resource teacher for the regular teacher to mark. In another area of support, specialist teachers also help the students identify landmarks to help them orientate themselves to their environment. According to Okyere and Adam (2003), resource teachers provide in-service training for the other teachers on how to manage the SEN child in learning. The techniques and methods of teaching some subjects are demonstrated for regular classroom teacher to adapt. In the community, the resource teachers target the schools, the clinics as well as going to homes to educate students and parents on disability issues. The provision of these services in most cases help pupils with special educational needs to adjust in the general education and they benefit from their education (Okyere& Adam, 2003).

3.3 Physician/Nurses Support

Regular classroom teachers again rely on the services of physician/nurses before they can render effective and efficient support for student with SEN in their schools. PL94-142 established the need for greater involvement of medical and health-related personnel in the education of students with special needs (Guralnick, 2002).

Levine (1992) noted that physician can aid the multidisciplinary team by performing diagnostic tests to assess the student's physical development, sensory abilities, medical problems, and central nervous system functioning; providing an understanding of nutrition, allergies, illnesses, and somatic symptoms; planning and monitoring the effectiveness of medication intervention; and discussing the potential side effects of drug interventions.

International council for Education of the visually impaired (2010) noted that some student may require the services of a medical specialist, who can meet the specific medical and physical needs of students including pupils with low vision by providing diagnostic and treatment services within their areas of specialization. For example, an ophthalmologist a medical doctor with a specialty in diagnosis and treatment of eye diseases and defeats. Treatment may include prescription of drugs, glasses, surgery or other therapy.

3.4 Psychological Support

As indicated earlier, regular classroom teachers count on the services of the school Psychologists in order to support pupils with special educational needs in their schools. An important member of the multidisciplinary team is the school psychologists. In many instances, teams are chaired by school Psychologists because of their training and expertise in the administration and interpretation of standardized tests. In addition to carrying out test-related tasks, school psychologists also collect data from regular teachers on pupils by observing them in their classrooms and interviewing regular teachers who work with the pupils with visual impairments in order to assist them.

Many school Psychologists are trained as consultants to assist regular classroom teachers in designing, implementing, and evaluating pre-referral interventions and behaviour management systems (Amponteng, 2014). Psychologists are professionals trained in the science of human behaviour and learning. They have expertise in the area of cognitive, behavioural, social and emotional development (Avoke, Hayford, Ihenacho, & Ocloo, 1998) cited in Amponteng (2014) stated that, psychologists offer services to both students with 'normal' and 'abnormal' development.

3.5 Material Resources/Support

The purpose of using instructional materials is to promote efficiency of education by improving the quality of teaching and learning. According to Ikerionwn (2000), instructional materials are objects or devices which help the teacher to make learning meaningful to learners. Aduwa-Ogiogbaen and Imogie (2005) claim these materials and resources including audio tape recorders, video tape recorders, slide projectors, opaque

projectors, overhead projectors, still pictures, programmed instruction, filmstrips, maps, charts, graphs and many more offer a variety of learning experiences individually or in combination to meet different teaching and learning experiences. It is common knowledge in the educational field that teaching at any level requires that the students are exposed to some form of simulation. Adekunle (2008) asserted that teaching resources are anything that can assist the teacher in promoting teaching and learning.

When pupils with special educational needs are given the chance to learn through more senses than one, they can learn faster and easier. Ezegebe (1994) classified instructional materials into two. To him, there are visual materials, made up of reading and non-reading materials and audio-visual materials comprising electrically operated and non-electrically operated materials. The use of instructional materials provides the teacher with interesting and compelling platforms for conveying information since they motivate learners to learn more. Furthermore, the teacher is assisted in overcoming physical difficulties that could have hindered his effective presentation of a given topic.

3.6 Use of Tactile Materials

Pauline (2008) noted that teachers must be aware, that students with visual impairments have deficit in conceptual experiences and understanding due to absence of visual ability, therefore adaptations of teaching materials become paramount, if they have to learn all the things other students without visual impairments learn in the class. To help this, therefore, these students should be taught physically using concrete experiences (Bishop, 1996; Pauline, 2008). Following this proposition, these pupils should be given an opportunity to explore tactile diagrams. Tactile diagrams are very important to understand images and concepts which are difficult to explain and describe in words. Therefore, they should apparently be used when shapes and patterns are very important to understand the concept but also, when the real objects are not available to help teaching (Salisbury, 2008). Tactile images or diagrams can be drawn on Braille papers using a special mat and stylus. This produces a relief image or diagram that can be easily felt (UNESCO, 2001). Teachers who teach blind children in inclusive classrooms need to provide adequate special materials and equipment.

There is almost universal agreement that the special materials and equipment needed by a visually impaired student in an inclusive school are essential to their success (Bina, 1993; Bishop, 1990; 1996; Hatlen, 1993; Holbrook, 1996; Kadmon, 1989; Kinos, 1993; Lebech, 1990; Lewis, 1994 cited in Amponteng (2014). Therefore, every creative effort to acquire the necessary materials and equipment should be explored. In addition, (Sacks et al., 1992; Hoben Lindstrom, 1980 cited in Amponteng, 2014) friendly user materials are good teaching materials for the visually impaired and creative materials which are provided to visually impaired children enhance dialogue and social interaction to complete an assignment. Pauline (2008) stated that the more significantly cognitively impaired the student, the greater the need for specialized materials, and the greater the need for the teacher's high expectations that will lead to success in reading. During the instruction of new materials, it is recommended that teachers who adhere to established

guidelines to maximize engagement should provide four to six opportunities per minute for students to respond. When students are working with learned during independent practice activities, the recommended number of opportunities to respond need to increase to 8-12 responses per minute with 90% accuracy. Even pupils with visual impairments whose knowledge of concepts is strong would have difficulty keeping pace with this rate of instruction, unless it is entirely verbal (Pauline, 2008).

3.7 Use of Real Objects in Teaching Students with special educational needs

According to Ocloo (2011), in education, realia are objects from real life used in classrooms instruction by educators to improve students' understanding of other cultures and real life situations. The author gave examples of such objects as ball, comb, scissors, toothbrush, zipper, string of beads and spoon among others. Again, the author stated that instructional materials help pupils with SEN understand concepts easily in the sense that they add concreteness to verbal explanation and description. Real objects, as aids, give the warmth and true life experiences to pupils with SEN. Pupils with low vision for instance can use their residual vision to see, handle and play with these concrete materials which eventually assist them to register the concept permanently in memory and this facilitates easy recall (Ocloo, 2011). Ewudo (2009) stated that instructional materials help pupils with SEN to improve in their learning procedure.

Through the use of instructional material, skills are developed. It also helps students in a range of experiences and to achieve their desired aim (Ewudo, 2009). Ogbu (2006) opined that real objects develop pupils' ideas through the creation of events and objectives which will improve the pupils' continuity of thought. Equally, instructional material facilitates, stimulates and aids students to take active interest in the subject under study. It improves the emotional instruct of students by providing them with the required knowledge. It improves students understanding of the working model introduced by the teacher. The pupils capture the true picture of what is taught by the teacher. In presenting subject content and motion pictures, real objects play an efficient role by making sure pupils captures the main points or the subject matter (Ogbu, 2006).

3.8 Use of Audio, Optical and Non-Optical Devices

Salisbury (2008) noted that since pupils with visual impairments rely mainly on verbal information for their learning, teachers need to incorporate audio devices to aid their teaching process. Audio devices include things like audiocassettes and compact discs. However, lesson contents with diagrams and tables cannot be well explained in an audio format (Salisbury, 2008). Moreover, teachers can tape record their lessons and give to students with visual impairments for later playback at their convenient time (UNESCO, 2001).

Moreover, if a video tape for example has to be shown, it is advisable for teachers to show it to students with visual impairment so that through a specialized teacher's or a classmate's explanation, they understand all the visual concepts in it before the class watches it. For a film with subtitles, a classmate or teacher can read aloud to the class to

help those with visual impairment (Spungin, 2002). Optical devices such as eyeglasses, magnifiers and telescopes use lenses to increase a person's residual vision. They are normally prescribed by a medical specialist while non-optical devices do not incorporate a lens and do not need to be prescribed by a specialist. Things like large prints, Braille and Braille writer, tape recorders, book stands, recorded and talking, books and calculators, are examples of non-optical devices (Simon, Echeita, Sandoval, & Lopez, 2010). The role of both optical and non-optical devices is to improve vision and increase functionality of pupils with visual impairments through the use of other senses. It is the role of a teacher to encourage students with visual impairment to use visual devices and assistive technologies to help them with vision (Spungin, 2002).

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3.9 Adaptive Teaching Methods for Supporting Pupils with SEN who have Low Vision to participate in teaching and learning activities.

Apart from human and material resources for providing support for pupils with special educational needs to participate in teaching and learning activities, adaptive teaching methods when properly use by teachers also play a central role in providing support for pupils with low vision. Some of these methods are shown below:

A. Adapting Written Texts

For teachers to be effective and efficient in assisting pupils with visual impairment, teaching materials need to be adapted. For example, printed text can be adapted through increasing the font size, bolding the text, increasing contrast, adding colour, and adjusting spaces between characters. However, the extent of these adaptations depends solely on the severity of visual defects and the needs of the pupil concerned (Bishop, 1996; Mastropieri & Scruggs, 2010). According to Spungin (2002), it is important to consult a specialist teacher on preparation of materials prior to the lesson; because different pupils use different materials depending on the degree of their visual impairment.

Meanwhile, regular teachers should provide students with low vision a copy of notes which are written on the chalkboard or presented on a projector. A specialized teacher for students with visual impairment, should help to clarify the lesson to them, and if possible, should teach them before the main teaching session starts (Spungin, 2002). If a teacher is writing on the chalkboard or uses visual aids, it is important that he or she

uses large writing text on the blackboard or visual aids in order to assist pupils with low vision. In addition, a teacher should use coloured chalks to assist pupils (UNESCO, 2001).

B. Use of Instructional Conversation

Best (1992) observed that since pupils with visual impairments do not see clearly, they rely on the voice of the teacher as one of the main sources of information for learning. It is therefore important for the teacher to do some or all of the following: Firstly, the voice of the teacher has to be pleasant. By pleasant, it means that it should produce relaxed tone and pitch (Best, 1992). The author also stated that, the voice of the teacher should be interesting to listen to. Speed of talking, volume and pitch are very important to make the voice interesting for students (Best, 1992). A teacher should avoid vague statements. Phrases like “over here” or “this and that” should be avoided as much as possible, because they do not help pupils with visual impairments to understand what a teacher is talking about (Mastropieri & Scruggs, 2010).

Spungin (2002) noted that during the teaching process a teacher should read the notes aloud while writing them on the board or presenting them on the projector. Mastropieri and Scruggs (2010) and Salisbury (2008) noted that teachers should call the names of pupils first when they want to address a particular pupil. Teachers should ask questions or give specific instructions so that pupils know specifically whom the teacher is talking to. This is important, because it helps pupils with visual impairments feel part of the class and lessons.

According to UNESCO (2001), it is equally important to use pupils’ names during class discussions so that pupils with visual impairments would be in the position to understand who is talking. Finally, the language that has been used for content delivery in the class has been a major hindrance for the level of engagement and academic achievement of some pupils, especially those with visual impairment. Therefore, it is equally important for teachers to use simple and clear language in the teaching and learning process (Grace & Gravestock, 2009; Hannell, 2007). Westwood (1995) stated that the best teacher is the one who uses simple presentation and communication. The best teacher also makes follow up on individual pupil’s tasks in order to make sure that they understand the lesson (Westwood, 1995).

C. Extra Time Allowance

According to Mastropieri and Scruggs (2010), pupils with low vision complete their work very slowly due to the nature of their impairment. Therefore, it is extremely important for classroom teachers to give extra time allowance for these pupils to process visual information, and complete their written assignments (Salisbury, 2008). Pupils with low vision take longer time to read a text than pupils with normal vision. Also reading and writing in Braille as well as getting information from tactile sources for pupils with visual impairment consumes a lot of time. At the same time, pupils with visual impairment need much time to integrate information coming through hearing (Mastropieri & Scruggs, 2010). Generally, it is acceptable for teachers to add half of the time for students with low

vision, and twice as much for pupils with blindness (Spungin, 2002). Many external examinations recognize this requirement and, therefore, teachers should give them allowance of up to 100% additional time for pupils with visual impairments (Salisbury, 2008).

D. Using Questions and Answers

According to Spungin (2002), oral method of giving instructions and getting responses from the pupils with low vision can also be a good option if general teachers use it. A teacher of pupils with low vision can write down the answers given out orally by a student with low vision. Moreover, a tape recorder can be used by teachers to record the answers the student is giving. However, through this way, a pupil cannot review the answers he or she has given for possible correction. Therefore, pupils with low vision and teachers of pupils with low vision should be consulted before the test is taken, in order to find a better way of assessing a pupil with low vision (Spungin, 2002).

E. Encouraging Collaborative Learning

Mastropieri and Scruggs (2010) opined that in the learning process pupils differ in capabilities perceived by teachers. Pupils with low ability will learn from their fellow capable peers. Cooperative learning among students of different learning capabilities and learning needs, in an inclusive classroom, has proved to be effective in promoting academic achievement, positive attitude towards the subject, and improving social interaction among students. For that reason, it is very important for inclusive classroom teachers employ cooperative learning when teaching pupils with low abilities (Mastropieri & Scruggs, 2010). Mitchell (2008) stated that cooperative group learning which involves learners working together in small learning groups could be adopted to facilitate collaborative activities among pupils. This helps students with special educational needs to assist each other to carry out different tasks. It is a good strategy of teaching students with special needs, particularly in the mixed ability groups. It is especially important in third world countries including Ghana where classes are very large (Mitchell, 2008). In these groups, regular teachers need to pair students with low abilities with their fellow high ability pupils who will help them to organize their works, and repeat teacher's instructions (UNESCO, 2001).

3.10 Types of Support

The inclusive education system requires some types of support to function effectively. The support to consider in this context is that from stakeholders in the form of teacher, parental and administrative support.

A. Teacher Support

Teacher support in the classroom is crucial for effective learning because not all students are capable of grasping curriculum content at the same rate. Some students enjoy more success in assimilating curriculum content and favourable teacher and peer interaction

than other students. Lewis and Doorlag (2003) emphasized what teacher's support in organizing the curriculum, grouping pupils, and setting up delivery systems for pupils' performance as well as their achievements. In support of this, Udvari-Solner (1992) cited by the National Information Centre for Children and Youth with Disabilities (NICHCY, 1995), talked about adaptation of the curriculum as teachers support. This means that, the teacher is expected to adjust the curriculum by breaking down the content to the level of the pupils taking into consideration their individual differences. Curricular adjustments differentiate content, and enable teachers to select contents for its real-life value for students based on their unique needs (Choate, 2000). Keogh (1990) notes that the key success for students with disability placed in the inclusive classroom is how the general classroom teacher provides efficient support to the child.

B. Parental Support

Parental supports involve the role that parents or family members play towards their wards education. Parental role is crucial in the education of all children but in education of children with special educational needs, the role of the parent is even more, especially, in choosing of programmes for their wards. Hornby (2000) contends that children's academic achievement is likely to be enhanced if parents and teachers work closely together. It must be noted that home-school relationship is important to enable parents and school work together to provide appropriate support for the pupils in the school and home. According to Polloway and Patton (1997), information that is shared between parents and teachers is extremely important to maintain a productive instructional and management program, as both parties need to be aware of the student's progress in each setting (school and home).

Parents offer a big contribution to the education of their children, and are potential sources of information about the academic ability of students with special educational needs. Parents know their children better; they know what their interests are and what things are good for them. They also know their educational needs, and can plan for the future on behalf of their children. They will also provide necessary information about social, physical and emotional development (Garner & Davies, 2001; Webster & Roe, 1998). Having this information, a teacher will strive to structure and modify his or her teaching to help pupils with special educational needs in the class (Spungin, 2002). Parents are also given a major role to play. Instead of sitting on the side-lines and being called to school to be informed of changes, they actually participate in decision-making that concerns making changes. Parents are to be involved in aspects of school, such as the assessment of their own children.

C. Administrative Support

Administrative support involves financial assistance provided by the government of Ghana and some Nongovernmental Organizations (NGOs) to basic schools in the country. The government of Ghana since independence regards education as a fundamental human right for all its citizens and has enshrined this right in the Legal

Framework of Education. The 1961 Education Act is the principal legislation concerning the right to education for all children in Ghana. The 1992 Republican Constitution of Ghana gives further provision and support for education as a basic human right for all Ghanaians. Article 38(2) states:

“The Government shall within two years after parliament first meets after coming into force of this constitution draw up a program for the implementation within the following ten years for the provision of a free, compulsory universal basic education. (Government of Ghana (GOV), 1992, p.40)

A 10-year Free Compulsory Universal Basic Education (fCUBE) Programme in 1996, a policy framework that will increase educational access to all children, emerged from the 1992 Constitution. This policy has three main themes: Improving quality of teaching and learning:

- 1) improving management efficiency;
- 2) increasing access and participation (GES, 2003).

The fCUBE policy Document of (1996) stated that, the government of Ghana remains the major source of financing of the fCUBE programme in collaboration with donor agencies like the World Bank, United States Agency for International Development (USAID), the European Union (EU), African Development Bank (ADB), Canada International Development Agency (CIDA), and the United Nations International Children Emergency Fund (UNICEF).

According to the fCUBE Document of (1996) donor agencies contribute between 10 to 30 percent annually to education financing. The most recent policy initiative is the ‘Capitation Grant’. This policy, which provides free feeding programme for vulnerable children in deprived settings, is to reinforce the existing fCUBE policy of attracting and retaining children in school (MOE, 2005). A total of 95 billion Ghana cedis, an equivalent of US\$ 10.4 million, was allocated for ‘Capitation Grant’ in 2006 (GES, 2006). Other institutions like churches, companies, and clubs also fund and support education.

3.11 Special Educational Support Services in Inclusive Classroom

Another factor that has been identified as very essential for the success of children with special educational needs is the availability of resources and support services (Jones, 2002).

Jones outlined the following as support services needed in inclusive schools:

- Collaboration between staff and specialists;
- Support staff as an integral part of the inclusive education process;
- Provision of appropriate technology to deliver the curriculum in inclusive education.

A. Collaboration between Staff and Specialists

Kugelmass (2001) asserted that collaborating with specialists on various issues allows for the provision of advice and guidance to the classroom teacher on interventions and programmes to be followed by those with additional educational needs. Underlying the movement in education towards collaborative consultation is the premise that there is more to be gained by the classroom teacher working closely with other professionals to solve problems, than by relying on ready-made prescriptions for intervention from outside experts (Westwood, 1997). The consultant in this process may be the school's special educational needs coordinator, psychologists, speech and language therapists or other professionals. Teachers often need more than advice and ideas; sometimes they need practical facilitative assistance, and this should be part of the role of the consultant as well (Rose & Howley, 2007).

B. Support staff as an Integral Part of the Inclusive Education Process

The role of support staff within the classroom has been identified as critical to the success of inclusion (Farrell, 2000). When teachers and support staff are able to work effectively together, it has been found that the problems associated with the severity of the pupil's learning difficulty can be diminished (Florian, 1998). The benefits of involving support staff in the classroom are reflected in an Ofsted report (2002) in England, which found that the quality of teaching was better in classes with support staff than in those without them. Research by Blatchford, Russell, Bassett, Brown and Martin (2004) also suggests that the presence of in-class support staff has an indirect effect on teaching by increasing pupil engagement and freeing up the teacher from other duties to focus more effectively on instruction. Additionally, the provision of support staff is seen as facilitating inclusion by bringing additional skills to the classroom, enabling joint planning and reducing pupil teacher ratios (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), 2005).

Where support staff is working on a one to one basis with pupils, this approach may be viewed as running counter to the philosophy and intent of inclusive education as it differentiates them from their peers. Lorenz (1998) noted that when an assistant is affiliated to the child, there is a real danger that the child will be prevented from forming relationships with his or her peers and may develop an unhelpful dependency on the support worker. The child with disability may also be at risk of becoming passive and developing a learned helplessness. But while support staff may initially spend the majority of the allotted time working directly with the pupil, there should be a gradual move toward them providing more support to the teacher by assisting with modifications to curriculum content, developing alternative resources and setting up student support networks in the class (Westwood, 1997). In-class support models have a number of advantages, including the transfer of skills to the classroom teacher, increased collaborative planning and greater opportunities for pupils to keep pace with classroom work (Griffin & Shevlin, 2007).

Lack of training for support staff has often been highlighted as an issue, particularly when they are working with students with high levels of additional needs. Farrell (2000) made the point that the training and expertise of support staff determines their ability to implement methods appropriate to children's needs and to work as part of a team. It is therefore important to provide a structured programme of continuing professional development for support staff working in schools. The training of support staff has been found to produce measurable social benefits for students with severe disabilities, including an increase in their level of interaction with peers (Causton-Theoharis & Malmgren, 2005). The use of support staff in classrooms is now a well-established practice and clearly has the potential to facilitate inclusion but more research is needed to assess the nature and impact of its role.

C. Provision of Appropriate Technology to deliver the Curriculum in Inclusive Education

Gardner (1996) stated that assistive technology is available to enable students with special educational needs to access the curriculum. Assistive technology is any item, piece of equipment or product system that is used to improve the functioning of individuals with disabilities. Besides the central issue of providing access to the curriculum, assistive technology also enhances pupil independence (an essential component in inclusion), and allows the pupil with special needs to actively participate in education. Pupils with a wide range of learning difficulties or disabilities can benefit from assistive technology. For example, a child with a hearing impairment may need a hearing aid to participate in class; a child with a visual impairment may benefit from a device that enlarges printed words; and a pupil with a learning difficulty may need a calculator to help with maths problems (Gardner, 1996). In addition, children who lack a reliable, understandable way of communicating may be helped through augmentative communication approaches, including language boards and devices with speech synthesizers. Assistive technology may also be used to help students' access and operate computers. Alternative keyboards and mice as well as other alternative methods of input such as pointing devices, switches, and touch-screens allow children with disabilities to operate computers (Gardner, 1996).

Some of the benefits of inclusive technology as identified by Gardner (1996) are summarised below:

- a. Pupils have greater control over their own learning experience.
- b. Pupils can participate in and contribute more fully in classroom activities and complete assignments independently.
- c. Pupils can interact to a greater extent with their typical peers, improving social skills and enhancing acceptance.

Information, Communication and Technology (ICT) offers ways of circumventing motor, communication, and learning difficulties, as well as providing applications specifically designed to teach particular skills, such as language comprehension or numeracy. A recent study in the UK examined the impact of computer use on learners with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) working on science tasks. The

results showed a significant improvement in the accuracy of responses and on-task behaviours (Shaw & Lewis, 2005). Information, Communication and Technologies also enable increased access to the curriculum and help pupils to consolidate and reinforce what has already been learned in the classroom. Everyday technologies such as email can be used to send home homework which is otherwise incompletely or inaccurately copied from the blackboard. Other technologies, such as interactive whiteboards have been used successfully in delivering curricula, allowing the lesson notes to be saved by the pupil for later reference, reinforcement and revision.

Gardner (1996) identified some of the benefits of ICT in delivering the curriculum to pupils as:

- a. **Individual attention:** Pupils respond well to the variety, structure, immediate reinforcement and the multi-sensory experiences offered by computer applications. Computers can be used to tailor instruction individually, and information rich multimedia programmes can enhance learning in specific subject areas, such as History or Geography.
- b. **Spell checker:** Using word processors in the writing process increases motivation because the child can see their work in a very readable and satisfactory manner; the spell checker reduces frustration and increases productivity, and is especially useful for those with dyslexia.
- c. **Text-to-speech:** Extremely useful for those with visual impairments or dyslexia, text-to-speech packages allow the student to hear what is written. Text to speech programmes can be used in conjunction with Optical Character Recognition software to “read in” text via a scanner and have it read back to the child. This is especially useful where the curriculum texts are not available in electronic format. Less high-tech solutions can also be useful, such as Dictaphones and tape recorders, and the use of audio books and curriculum texts.
- d. **Training specific skills:** Instructional computer software packages which are designed to develop specific skills such as literacy or numeracy are available for all age groups. Many of these applications are also good at assessing the child’s progress, both for the purposes of moving the child on through the programme at an appropriate pace and providing valuable feedback to the teacher.
- e. **Planning tools:** There is a growing number of ‘Mind-Mapping’ packages available. These are generally based on techniques which have been suggested by people like Tony Buzan (Buzan & Buzan, 1993) but which have been made much easier by the arrival of suitable technology. This software can have a wealth of uses both in planning a piece of writing and retaining information in an organised form.

Using assistive technology as a tool for curriculum access is rapidly evolving approach to education. The continuous advancements in technology will only help to expand its application in the inclusive classroom. Some studies have been conducted in various regions of the world (Talmor, Reiter & Feign, 2005; Mayaba 2008; British Colombia Teachers Federation (BCTF), 2006 and Schumm & Vaughn, 1996). In a study conducted in Pietermaritzburg, South Africa in 2008, Mayaba examined educators’

perceptions and experiences on inclusive education in selected schools (Talmor, Reiter & Feign, 2005). A semi-structured questionnaire adopted from the British Columbia Teachers Federation (BCTF), work life of Teachers survey series 2: Special Education (BCTF, 2006) was used for the study. From the study, it was revealed that teachers in South Africa generally do not support Inclusive Education. First, respondents identified problems which they encounter in the implementation of inclusive practices in their classrooms. Moreover, respondents indicated that they lack sufficient resources, expertise or training on Inclusive Education (Talmor, Reiter & Feign, 2005).

In conclusion, teachers indicated in the study that they see themselves as unprepared to teach children with varying degrees of disability in their schools. Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made. First, there was a recommendation that appropriate resources for teaching should be provided for teachers in inclusive schools. Emphasis should also be placed on training skills for such educators to recognise the ability of every child to learn with emphasis on the child's strengths rather than on their weaknesses (Talmor, Reiter & Feign, 2005).

3.12 Remedial Measures for helping Pupils with Special Needs

Reber and Reber (2001), describe the term 'remedial' as a training or educational programme designed to correct deficiencies and to elevate the learner or trainee to an acceptable level. Sampson (1975) also sees remedial teaching as a type of teaching which rectifies some deficiency or puts things right. This means that remedial teaching is conscious efforts made by teachers to support students learn concepts after the normal classroom teaching.

Beveridge (1999), is of the view that all children can be regarded as having special needs of some kind during their school careers. Smith, Polloway, Patton & Dowdy (1998), state that over 11 percent of the school-age children in the United States of America, or approximately 5.3 million learners are classified as having barriers to learning. The Warnock Report suggests that as many as 20 percent of children in regular schools' experience difficulties in their school life hence, the need for remedial measures or teaching for pupils with special educational needs.

Teaching pupils with special educational needs in the inclusive classroom involves adaptation and modification. Teachers have to adapt or modify the regular curriculum to meet the needs of these pupils. Pupils with special educational needs require more instructional time and other learning methods. They also need teaching and learning material and real objects in their teaching and learning process. Teachers must therefore employ the use of various learning approaches that motivate learners and boost their interest in the remedial teaching process. Farrell & Balshaw (2002) stress on the use of teaching assistants as remedial measure for pupils with special educational needs. The use of teaching assistants in an inclusive classroom is a common practice in countries like England. In South Africa, it was estimated that, during the year 2000, there was as many as 80,000 teaching assistants working in regular schools. This practice makes it easy for

teachers to do remedial teaching to support pupils with special educational needs to be successful in inclusive schools.

4. Methodology

The study used basically a survey design which employed the quantitative approach to investigate how children with special Learning Needs (SENs) are supported to learn together in the inclusive classroom with the focus on finding the level of support for children in five inclusive schools in the Cape Coast Metropolis, Ghana. The sample size involved 86 teachers, 6 administrators (Head teachers) and 40 parents. In all, a total of 132 participants were involved in the study. Questionnaire was designed in close-ended format for the teachers, administrators and parents. The basic structure of the instrument was based on four Point Likert-type scales. The Likert-scale items questionnaire was analysed using frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviation. A tally sheet was used to generate frequency counts out of which percentages were calculated based on the scores assigned to each rating. These data were then analysed using the SPSS computer system.

5. Discussion, Analysis and Presentation of Findings

Research Question 1: What Levels of Support is Required for Meeting the Differential Learning Needs of Pupils with Special Educational Needs in Inclusive Classroom?

The first research question was to find out the level of support that was required to meet the needs of pupils with special educational needs in inclusive classrooms. To answer this research question, respondents' responses to the questionnaire items number 1 to 8 were used.

Table 1 shows teachers' responses to items 1- 8 which were used to answer research question 1. The results in Table 1 clearly show that 4 (4.7%) of the teachers strongly agreed that classrooms are accessible to support all pupils, 32 (37.2%) agreed to the statement, 27 (31.4%) disagreed with the statement and 23 (26.7%) strongly disagreed. An inference from the above is that majority of the teachers disagreed that classrooms are accessible to support all pupils. This could be attributed to the fact that most of the basic school infrastructure in Cape Coast Metropolis is not disability friendly.

As a result of that most children with special educational needs will find it difficult to adjust to school environment which might lead to poor performance. Bennetts and Flynn (2002) stated that, in order to provide inclusive education, the physical environment needs to be safe and accessible to all pupils, including those with physical and sensory disabilities.

Table 1: Teachers Responses on Material/Human Support for Pupils with Special Educational Needs (N=86)

	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD
		F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)		
1	Classrooms are accessible to support all pupils with special educational needs in my school.	4 (4.7)	32 (37.)	27 (31.)	23 (267)	2.8023	.8921
2	Classroom seating arrangements support inclusive of pupils with special needs.	31 (36.0)	19 (22.1)	26 (30.2)	10 (11.6)	2.1744	1.0538
3	A resource room for pupils with special need is needed to support pupil performance.	65 (75.6)	17 (19.8)	0 (0)	4 (4.7)	1.2907	.55021
4	The school receives materials from GES to support the teaching of pupils with special needs.	3 (3.5)	17 (19.8)	27 (31.4)	27 (31.4)	3.0465	.81033
5	Pupils with special educational needs lack some resources that support their learning in class.	40 (46.5)	43 (50.0)	1 (1.2)	2 (2.3)	1.5930	.63945
6	Resource teachers cooperate with me to support pupils with special needs.	22 (25.6)	28 (32.6)	22 (25.6)	14 (16.3)	2.3256	1.0340
7	Related services such as screening, audiology services are functional in my school to support SEN pupils.	7 (8.1)	18 (20.9)	25 (29.1)	36 (41.9)	3.0465	.981
8	ICT services are available to support all pupils including those with special educational needs in my school.	7 (8.1)	13 (15.1)	46 (53.5)	20 (23.3)	2.9186	.84317
	Average					2.410	1.091

Source: Field data (2016).

From Table 1, out of the 86 respondents, 31 (36.0%) of them strongly agreed that the classroom seating arrangements do not support inclusion of pupils with special educational needs, 19 (22.1%) agreed to the statement, 26 (30.2%) disagreed that classroom seating arrangements do not support inclusion of pupils with special needs and 10 (11.6%) also strongly disagreed with the statement. A deduction from the above is that majority of the teachers strongly agreed that the classroom seating arrangements do not support inclusion of pupils with special educational needs in class. The implication is that this will adversely affect the performance of children with special educational needs in the inclusive classroom. This is because; these children must be given a comfortable seating place in inclusive classroom to be able to access the school curriculum effectively.

In support of this Bennetts and Flynn (2002) stated that teachers can help children with special educational needs to access the school curriculum by modifying the seating arrangement to meet the needs of children with special educational needs. Rivera-Batiz and Marti (1995) also opined that the seating arrangements in classrooms can be structured to enable not only greater physical access for all pupils, and access to the point of learning, but also as a means of controlling unwanted behaviour for those with behavioural difficulties. For example, furniture and equipment can be arranged in such a way as to reduce unwanted movement around the classroom and minimise

opportunities for pupils to disrupt other pupils at their workspaces. Pupils with visual or hearing impairments can be seated close to the blackboard or teacher, or next to a window to avail extra natural light. Likewise, students who may need more frequent monitoring or have difficulties staying on task should also be considered for preferential seating near the teacher, or between well-focused pupils, away from distractions).

The results in Table 2 indicates that 65 (75.6%) of the teachers strongly agreed that a resource room for pupils with special educational needs is needed to support students' performance, 17 (19.8%) agreed to the statement and 4 (4.7%) strongly disagreed that a resource room for students with special educational needs is needed to support pupils' performance. A deduction from the above is that majority of the respondents strongly agreed that a resource room for pupils with special educational needs is needed to support pupils' performance.

With the responses of item 4 in Table 1, 3 (3.5%) of the teachers strongly agreed that the school receives materials from GES to support teaching, 17 (19.8%) agreed to the statement, 39 (45.3%) disagreed with the statement and 27 (31.4%) also strongly disagreed that the school receives materials from GES to support teaching. The responses obtained clearly shows that majority of the teachers disagreed that the school receives materials from GES to support teaching. Ghana Education Service play a vital role in the education of children in the country because they are the only Department under the Ministry of Education mandated by the constitution of Ghana to provide services and materials / equipment for the education of all children including those with special educational needs in basic and second cycle institutions in Ghana. Therefore, if they do not provide the needed material support to teachers in the inclusive classroom, teaching and learning will not be successful.

Out of the 86 respondents sampled, 40 (46.5%) of the teachers strongly agreed that pupils with special educational needs lack some resources that they need to support teaching in the classroom, 43 (50.0%) also agreed to the statement, 1 (1.2%) disagreed to the statement and 2 (2.3%) strongly disagreed that students with special educational needs lacked some resources that they need to support teaching in the classroom. Thus, majority of the teachers agreed that pupils with special needs lacked some resources that they need in the classroom. Children with special educational needs require certain resources such as magnifiers, computers, and calculators to support their learning in the inclusive classroom. Therefore, when these resources are not available in the inclusive classroom for children with special educational needs, it will limit their ability to perform creditably.

Table 1 depicts that 22 (25.6%) of the teachers strongly agreed that resource teachers cooperate with them to support pupils with special needs, 28 (32.6%) agreed to the statement, 22 (25.6%) disagreed and 14 (16.3%) also strongly disagreed that resource teachers cooperate with them to support pupils with special educational needs. It can be said that majority of the teachers agreed that resource teachers cooperate with them to support students with special educational needs. This is a very good indication because educating children with special educational needs cannot be the sole responsibility of the

general education teacher. Rather, they must collaborate with special education teachers, parents, head teachers and other professionals to provide comprehensive services to children with special educational needs. For a general education teacher to be effective in inclusive classroom, he or she requires skills in consulting other professionals in various fields for more insight into various behaviours and characteristics exhibited by students in inclusive classrooms. Engelbrecht and Green (2001) supported this assertion by noting that teachers need knowledge on how to make consultation so that when there is the need for more specialist guidance and intervention, the teacher can draw support from these personnel who will be capable of offering such support and advice to him or her. Kugelmass (2001) also asserted that collaborating with specialists on various issues allows for the provision of advice and guidance to the classroom teacher on interventions and programmes to be followed by those with additional educational needs.

As indicated on Table 1, 7 (8.1%) of the teachers strongly agreed that related services such as screening, audiology services function well in their school to support SEN pupils, 18 (20.9%) agreed to the statement, 25 (29.1%) disagreed to the statement and 36 (41.9%) strongly disagreed that related services such as screening and audiology services function well in their school to support SEN students. From this, it can be seen that majority of the teachers strongly disagreed that related services such as screening and audiology services function well in their school to support SEN pupils.

Out of the 86 respondents, 7 (8.1%) of the teachers strongly agreed that ICT services are available to support all pupils including those with special needs, 13 (15.1%) also agreed to the statement, 46 (53.5%) disagreed to the statement and 20 (23.3%) strongly disagreed that ICT services are available to support all pupils including those with special needs. A deduction from the above is that majority of the teachers disagreed that ICT services are available to support all pupils including those with special educational needs. This finding has negative consequences on the education of children with special educational needs and disabilities. This is because Information, Communication and Technology (ICT) offers ways of circumventing motor, communication, and learning difficulties, as well as providing applications specifically designed to teach particular skills, such as language comprehension or numeracy. A study conducted by Shaw and Lewis (2005) in UK showed that information communication technology has significant improvement in the accuracy of responses and on-task behaviours of children with attention deficit hyperactivity disorders (ADHD).

Again, the mean of means helped to find out the overall material or human support required to meet the differential learning needs of pupils with special educational needs in inclusive classrooms in respondents' various schools.

Overall, the mean of means of the levels of support required for meeting the differential learning needs of pupils in inclusive classrooms with special educational needs recorded a value of 2.4. This implies that selected schools have low levels of material or human support for pupils with special educational needs in inclusive classroom. The finding supports the work of Mushoriwa (2001), who concluded that most schools do not have material or human support required to satisfy the needs of pupils

with special educational needs. Griffin and Shevlin (2007), also confirmed this research as the findings of the study reflected that most selected schools do not have much material support for pupils with special educational needs in inclusive classroom.

Research Question 2: What Educational Support Exist for Pupils with Special Educational Needs in Inclusive Classroom?

To answer this research questions, teachers’ responses to questionnaire items number 9 to 15 were used. Table 3 shows the teachers’ responses to the items.

Table 2 shows responses to items 9 to 15 which were used to answer research question 2.

Table 2: Teachers Responses on Special Educational Support that Exist for Pupils with Special Educational Needs in Inclusive Classroom (N=86)

	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD
		F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)		
9	Individualized teaching is actively practiced in my school to support with pupils with special educational needs.	0 (0)	25 (29.1)	46 (53.5)	15 (17.4)	2.8837	.6760
10	Indirect services such as supporting the class teacher to plan an IEP, select the right materials for pupils with special educational needs is practiced.	3 (3.5)	20 (23.3)	42 (48.8)	21 (24.4)	2.9419	.78747
11	I support SEN pupils by giving enough time for learners to manipulate instructional materials to facilitate learning.	16 (18.6)	36 (41.9)	27 (31.4)	6 (7.0)	2.5000	2.28936
12	I use facilities and instructional materials to support pupils with SEN.	0 (0)	16 (18.6)	43 (50.0)	27 (31.4)	3.1279	.69952
13	There are no models in school to support learning.	18 (20.9)	21 (24.4)	31 (36.0)	16 (18.6)	2.5233	1.02586
14	My school has a resource room to support pupils with SEN.	5 (5.8)	32 (37.2)	21 (24.4)	28 (32.6)	2.8372	.95622
15	I use remedial teaching in my school to support pupils with SEN.	2 (2.3)	31 (36.0)	26 (30.2)	27 (31.4)	2.9070	.87619

Source: Field data (2016).

As regards item 9 which was to find out whether individualized was actively practiced in the schools, a total of 25 (29.1%) of the teachers agreed that individualised teaching is actively practiced in their school to support pupils with special educational needs, 46 (53.5%) disagreed with the statement and 15 (17.4%) strongly disagreed that individualised teaching is actively practiced in their school to support pupils with special needs. An inference from the above is that majority of the teachers disagreed that individualized teaching is actively practiced in their school to support pupils with special needs. This may be as a result of the large class size in inclusive schools in Cape Coast Metropolis. When teachers are made to teach large class sizes, they find it difficult to provide individualized teaching. Many things happen when children are taught in sizes

manageable by the teacher. Individual attention may be given as well as provision of prompt feedbacks. When learner's needs are in focus, there is the probability of high tasks performance and high expectation of success. This therefore means that stake holders of education must ensure that class sizes in inclusive schools are reduced to the minimum number that teachers can manage effectively so that individualised teaching can be provided.

From Table 2, item 10, out of the 86 respondents, 3 (3.5%) of them strongly agreed that indirect services such as supporting the class teacher to plan an IEP, select the right materials for students with SEN is practiced in my school, 20 (23.3%) agreed to the statement, 42 (48.8%) disagreed that indirect services such as supporting the class teacher to plan an IEP, select the right materials for pupils with SEN is practiced in my school and 21 (24.4%) also strongly disagreed with the statement. A deduction from the above is that majority of the teachers disagree that indirect services such as supporting the class teacher to plan an IEP and selecting the right materials for pupils with SEN are practiced in the schools.

The results in Table 2, item 11 indicates that 16 (18.6%) of the teachers strongly agreed that they support SEN pupils by giving enough time for learners to manipulate instructional materials to facilitate learning, 36 (41.9%) agreed to the statement, 27 (31.4%) disagreed with the statement and 6 (7.0%) strongly disagreed that they gave enough time for learners to manipulate instructional materials to facilitate learning. A deduction from the above is that majority of the respondents agreed that they supported SEN pupils by giving them enough time to manipulate instructional materials to facilitate learning.

With the responses of item 12 in Table 2, 16 (18.6%) of the teachers agreed that they use facilities and instructional materials for supporting pupils with SEN in their schools, 43 (50.0%) disagreed with the statement and 27 (31.4%) also strongly disagreed that they use facilities and instructional materials for supporting pupils with SEN in their school. The responses obtained clearly shows that majority of the teachers disagreed that they used facilities and instructional materials for supporting pupils with SEN in their school. This indicates that teaching and learning materials were not adequate in inclusive schools in Cape Coast Metropolis and may impede the success of teaching and learning.

Heveveld (1994) posits that there would be no successful inclusive education if there is no availability of instructional materials. He insisted that because of the peculiar conditions of children with SEN, they require enhanced teaching and learning. This is achieved through efficient teaching and learning materials such as overhead projectors, public address systems, lighters amongst others. Simon, Echeita, Sandoval and Lopez (2010) support the position of Heveveld. They revealed that things like large prints, braille and braille writer, tape recorders, book stands and talking books and calculators are prerequisite for successful inclusive education. This was lacking in the study area as the teachers made it known to the researcher. With the responses of item 14 on the Table 2, 5 (5.8%) of the teachers strongly agreed that their school has a resource room to support pupils with SEN, 32 (37.2%) agreed to the statement, 21 (24.4%) disagreed with the statement and 28 (32.5%) also strongly disagreed that their school has a resource room to

support pupils with SEN. The responses obtained clearly shows that majority of the teachers agreed that their school has a resource room to support students with SEN.

On the item on remedial teaching, out of the 86 respondents, 2 (2.3%) of the teachers strongly agreed that they used remedial teaching in their school to support pupils with SEN, 31 (36.0%) also agreed to the statement, 26 (30.2%) disagreed to the statement and 27 (31.4%) strongly disagreed that they used remedial teaching in their school to support pupils with SEN. A deduction from the above is that majority of the teachers agreed that they used remedial teaching in their school to support pupils with SEN. The finding supports the work of Sreekumari (2003).

5.1 School Administrators' Report on Material Support for Students with Special Educational Needs

On the other hand, the school administrators also stated that the school does not receive any special materials from GES to support the education of SEN pupils. Special equipment like hearing aids, Braille machines, and magnifiers are not provided by GES to support the education of SEN pupils. They also indicated that the school does not get financial assistance from NGO's to support special educational needs. The details are provided in Table 3.

Table 3 shows administrators' data on material support used to support the analysis of research question 2.

Table 3: Administrators Responses on Material Support (N=6)

Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD
	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)		
20 My school receives support from GES to support SEN pupils' education.	0 (0)	2 (33.4)	4 (66.6)	0 (0)	3.000	0.000
21 My school receives support from NGO to support SEN pupils' education.	0 (0)	1 (16.6)	5 (83.3)	0 (0)	3.333	.5164
22 My school receives special equipment support from GES to support SEN pupils' education.	0 (0)	2 (33.4)	4 (66.6)	0 (0)	3.333	.5164

Source: Field data, (2016).

On personal support, majority of the administrators indicated that they collaborate with teachers in supporting pupils with special educational needs in their school, encourage teachers to do individualized teaching to support SEN pupils in their school and guidance and counseling services are rendered in their school to support pupils with special educational needs in their school. Again, most of the administrators stated that indirect services such as supporting the class teacher to plan IEP, select the right materials are provided in their school and resource teachers are not attached to the school to facilitate the inclusion of pupils with special educational needs. The findings are consistent with Killen (2006) who concluded that school administration support teachers with aids in teaching children with special needs. However, the findings do not agree

with the work done by Swain, French and Cameran (2003). The details of their responses are provided in Table 3.

Table 4 shows administrators' data on personal support used to support the analysis of research question 2.

Table 4: Administrators Responses on Personal Support (N=6)

	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. D
		F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)		
23	I collaborate with teachers to support pupils with SEN.	1 (16.7)	5 (83.3)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1.833	0.4082
24	I encourage teachers to do individualized teaching to support pupils with SEN.	0 (0)	6 (100.0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	2	0
25	Guidance and counselling services are rendered to pupils with special needs.	0 (0)	4 (66.7)	2 (33.3)	0 (0)	2.333	0.5164
27	Indirect services are available.	0 (0)	4 (66.7)	2 (33.3)	0 (0)	2.333	0.5164
26	Resource teachers are available.	0 (0)	1 (16.7)	4 (66.7)	1 (16.7)	3	0.632

Source: Field Data (2016).

Additionally, the parents also provided their responses on the personal support they provide to pupils with special needs. They indicated that they provide relevant information about their children to teachers and head teachers; they collaborate with teachers and head teachers to provide the needed educational support to their children. Majority of the parents stated that they form part of individualized educational plan team to support their children in school, they monitor their children's progress at school, and they see to the general wellbeing of their children. It was evident from the analysis that, the development of children with special needs was a key priority for these parents. This finding is consistent with Nabors, Willoughby, Leff, and McMenamin (2008) who examined how parents can support children with special needs in cooperative interactions. Again, Studies by Power and Hyde (2005) have reported the desire of parents to support their children with special needs. Polloway and Patton (1997), also stated that information that is shared between parents and teachers is extremely important to maintain a productive instructional and management program, as both parties need to be aware of the pupil's progress in each setting (school and home). Griffin and Shevlin (2007) in a study conducted in Bristol found out that parents are important stakeholders so far as inclusive education is concerned. They explained that parents provide relevant information about their children to teachers and head teachers were very important requirement for success. This position is consistent with the finding of the current study.

Hornby (2000) declares that children's academic achievement is likely to be enhanced if parents and teachers work closely together. One of the ways for the closeness is the formation of PTAs. Downing (2008) believes that even though it is worthwhile for

parents to attend PTA meetings it is not a panacea to the numerous problems associated with inclusive education from the perspective of parents. The details are provided in Table 5.

Table 5 shows parents responses to items 27 to 31 on personal support used to support the analysis on research Question 2.

Table 5: Parents Responses on Personal Support (N= 40)

Statement		SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD
		F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)		
28	Provision of information to authorities	20 (50)	20 (50.0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1.500	.512
29	Collaboration with school authorities to support their children's education	18 (40.0)	22 (60.0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1.600	.502
30	I form part of individualized education plan team	0 (0)	24 (70.0)	16 (30.0)	0 (0)	2.300	.470
31	Monitor my child's progress in school	10 (25.0)	20 (50.0)	10 (25.0)	0 (0)	2.050	.604
32	I see to the general wellbeing of my children	14 (35.0)	26 (65.0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1.800	.410

Source: Field data, (2015).

5.2 Summary of findings

Research Question 1

It was found from the study that there are low levels of material or human support for pupils with special educational needs in inclusive classrooms.

Research Question 2

On material support, the parents indicated that their children do not receive any material support from GES to support their children and they do not get any financial support from Non-Governmental Organisations (NGO's). On personal support, majority of the administrators indicated that they collaborate with teachers in supporting pupils with special educational needs in their school, individualized teaching is practiced in their school and guidance and counseling services are rendered to students with special educational needs in their school.

5.3 Conclusions

The study also concluded that inclusive education is possible, but its success would be achieved with the provision of the needed supports from teachers, parents and administrators in the form of instructional materials, infrastructure and many others.

5.4 Recommendations

- 1) Teachers must provide more material or human support for pupils with special educational needs in inclusive classrooms to improve their academic work.

- 2) Again, it is recommended that teachers, parents and administrators should come together to provide the needed support for pupils with special education needs to ensure the success of the inclusive agenda.

5.5 Suggestions for Further Research

This study was done in the Central Region of Ghana and more specifically, the Cape Coast Metropolis. The researcher, therefore, recommends that similar studies be done in other regions to ascertain what the situations may be.

References

- Aduwa-Ogiegbaen, S. O., & Imogie, A. I. (2005). *Instructional communication and technology in higher education*, Ibadan: Stirling Hordon Publishers (Nig) Ltd.
- Amponteng, M. (2014). *An assessment of resources available for pupils with special needs in general basic schools. A case study of Wiamoase educational circuit in the Sekyere south District-Ashanti region of Ghana*. Unpublished Master's Thesis. Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Kumasi-Ghana.
- Avoke, M. K., Hayford, S. K., Ihenacho, I. K., & Ocloo, M. A. (1998). *Issues in special education*. Accra: City Publishers.
- Baine, D. (2001). *Handicapped children in developing countries: Assessment curriculum and instruction*. Detroit: Vector.
- Bennetts, L. K., & Flynn, M. C. (2002). Improving the classroom listening skills of children with down syndrome by using sound-field amplification. *Down Syndrome Research and Practice*, 8(1), 19-24
- Best, A.B. (1992). *Teaching children with visual impairments*. Milton Keynes: Open University Press.
- Beveridge, S. (1999). *Special educational needs in school* (2nd ed.). London: Routledge.
- Bishop, V. (1996). *Teaching visually impaired children* (2nd ed.). New York: Charles C Thomas Publisher.
- Bishop, V. (1996). *Teaching visually impaired children* (2nd ed.). New York: Charles C Thomas Publisher.
- Blatchford, P., Russell, A., Bassett, P., Brown, P., & Martin, C. (2004). *The role and effects of teaching assistants in English primary schools (Years 4 to 6) 2000-2003: Results from the Class Size and Pupil Adult Ratios (CSPAR) KS2 project*. Research Report RR605. London: DfES.
- Buzan, T., & Buzan, B. (1993). *The mind map book*. London: BBC Books.
- Causton-Theoharis, J., & Malmgren, K. (2005). Increasing peer interactions for students with severe disabilities via paraprofessional training. *Exceptional Children*, 71(4), 431-444.
- Choate, J. S. (2000). *Successful inclusive teaching: Proven ways to detect and correct special needs*. Maryland: Allyn and Bacon.

- Downing, J. E. (2008). *Including students with severe and multiple disabilities in typical classrooms*. Baltimore: Paul Brookes Publishing Company.
- Engelbrecht, P., Green, L., Naicker, S., & Engelbrecht, P. (2004). *Inclusive education in action in South Africa*. Pretoria: Van Schaik.
- Ewudo, O. (2009). *Instructional materials: Impact on teachers*. Annual conference organized by the Education Department, Abia State University, Uturu.
- Ezegbe, M. O. (1994). Social Studies curriculum and instruction. In G. W. Joof, & H. C Amadi, (Eds). *Social Studies in schools: teaching methods, techniques, approaches and perspectives*. Onitsha, Nigeria, Outrite Publishers.
- Farrell, M. (2000). The impact of research on developments in inclusive education. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 4(2), 53-162.
- Farrell, M. (2000). The impact of research on developments in inclusive education. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 4(2), 53-162.
- Florian, L. (1998). Inclusive practice – What, why and how? In C. Tilstone, L. Florian, & R. Rose (Eds). *Promoting inclusive practice*. London: Routledge.
- Gardner, H. (1996). *The unschooled mind: How children think and schools should teach*. New York: Basic Books.
- Garner, P., & Davies, J. D. (2001). *Introducing special educational needs: A companion guide for student teachers*. London: David Fulton Publishers.
- Ghana Education Service (2006). *Education Strategic Plan*. Accra: Author.
- Grace, S., & Gravestock, P. (2009). *Inclusion and diversity: Meeting the needs of all students*. New York: Routledge: Taylor & Francis group. Grol.
- Griffin, S.R. & Shevlin, H.G (2007). *Change in Special Education: What brings it about?* London: Cassell.
- Guralnick. M. J. (2002). *Early childhood inclusion: Focus of change*. Baltimore, MD: Paul H. Brakes.
- Hornby, G. (2000). *Improving parental involvement*. London: Case II.
- International Council for Education of the visually impaired (2010). Retrieved from <http://www.worldblindunion.org/en/documents/e-bulletin/WBU-E-Bulletin-0710-July-10.doc>.
- Jones, P. (2002). Promoting inclusive practices in primary initial teacher training: Influencing hearts as well as minds. *Support for Learning*, 17(20), 58-63.
- Keogh, B. K. (1990). Narrowing the gap between policy and practice. *Exceptional Children*, 57, 186-190.
- Kugelmass, J. (2001). Collaboration and compromise in creating and sustaining an inclusive school. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 5(1), 47-65.
- Kugelmass, J. (2001). Collaboration and compromise in creating and sustaining an inclusive school. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 5(1), 47-65.
- Levine, M. (1992). *Developmental variations and learning disorders*. Cambridge, MA: Educators Publishing Service, Inc.
- Lewis, R. B., & Doarlag, D. A. (2003). *Teaching special student in general education classroom*. Pennsylvania: Merrill Prentice Hall.

- Lorenz S. (1998). *Effective in class support: The management of support staff in mainstream and special schools*. London: David Fulton.
- Mastropieri, M. A., & Scruggs, T. E. (2010). *The Inclusive Classroom: Strategies for effective differentiated Instruction*. New Jersey: Upper Saddle River.
- Ministry of Education (2005). *Education strategic plan: Policy targets and strategies*, volume 1. Accra: Ghana Publishing Company.
- Mitchell, D. (2008). *What really works in special and inclusive education: Using evidence-based teaching strategies*. London: Routledge.
- Mushoriwa, T. (2001). A study of attitudes of primary school teachers in Harare toward the inclusion of blind children in regular classes. *British Journal of Special Education*, 28 (3), 142-147.
- Nabors, L., Willoughby, J., Leff, S., & McMenamin, S. (2008). Promoting inclusion for young children with special needs on playgrounds. *Journal of Developmental and Physical Disabilities*, 13(2), 23-28.
- Ocloo, M. A. (2011). *Effective education for persons with visual impairments in Ghana*. Winneba: Department of Special Education.
- OFSTED, (2002). *Teaching assistants in primary schools: An evaluation of the quality and impact of their work*. London: Author.
- Ogbu, J. U. (2006). Understanding cultural diversity and learning. *Educational Research*, 21, 5-13.
- Okyere, A. B., & Adams, S. J. (2003). *Introduction of special education. An African perspective*. Accra: Adwinsa Publications (GH) Ltd.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2005). *Students with disabilities, learning difficulties and disadvantages: Statistics and indicators*. Paris: Author.
- Pauline, D. (2008). *Including children with visual impairment in mainstream schools: A practical guide*. London: David Fulton Publishers.
- Polloway, E. A., & Patton, J. R. (1997). *Strategies for teaching learners with special need*. New Jersey Prentice-Hall, Inc.
- Reber, A. & Reber, E. (2001). *The penguin dictionary of psychology* (3rd ed.). London: Penguin Books.
- Rivera-Batiz, F. L., & Marti, L. (1995). *A school system at risk: A study of the consequences of overcrowding in New York City public schools*. New York: Institute for Urban and Minority Education, Teachers College, Columbia University.
- Rose, R., & Howley, M. (2007). *Special educational needs in inclusive primary classrooms*. London: Paul Chapman.
- Salisbury, R. (2008). *Teaching pupils with visual impairment: A guide to making the school curriculum accessible*. London: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Sampson, O. C. (1995). *Remedial education*. London: Routledge Kegan Paul.
- Shaw, R., & Lewis, V. (2005). The impact of computer-mediated and traditional academic task presentation on the performance and behaviour of children with ADHD. *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, 5(2), 47-54.

- Simon, C., Echeita, G., Sandoval, M., & Lopez, M. (2010). *The inclusive education process of students with visual impairment in Spain: An analysis from the perspective of organizations*. Madrid: Alton Contents.
- Simon, C., Echeita, G., Sandoval, M., & Lopez, M. (2010). *The inclusive education process of students with visual impairment in Spain: An analysis from the perspective of organizations*. Madrid: Alton Contents.
- Spungin, S. J. (2002). *When you have a visually impaired student in your classroom: A guide for teachers*. New York: AFB Press.
- Talmor, R., Retiy, S., & Feigin, N, (2005). Factors relating to regular Education teacher burnout in inclusive education. *European Journal of Special Needs Education, 20*(2), 215-226.
- UNESCO (2001). *Understanding and responding to children needs in inclusive classrooms: A guide for Teachers*. Paris: Author.
- Westwood, P. (1995). *Effective Teaching*. Paper presented at the North West Region Inaugural Special Education Conference: Priorities, Partnerships (and Plum Puddings), Armidale.
- Westwood, P. (1997). *Common sense methods for children with special needs*. London: Routledge.

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